

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE RECEPTIVE AND PRODUCTIVE KNOWLEDGE OF COLLOCATIONS THROUGH INCIDENTAL LEARNING VS. INTENTIONAL LEARNING

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Abstract

The present study aimed to explore (a) whether incidental learning as compared with intentional learning leads to a more successful development of the receptive knowledge of collocations and (b) whether incidental learning as compared with intentional learning leads to a more successful development of the productive knowledge of collocations. Based on the study purpose and the participants' availability, 50 Persian-speaking high-intermediate female students from Kermanshah Iran Language Institute participated in the study. 25 students were assigned to the control group and 25 to the experimental group. Afterwards, the pretest in the form of a receptive and productive collocation test was given to both groups to find their familiarity with collocations. After 20 sessions of instruction, the posttest which was the same test as the pretest was administered to see the result of the treatment. The results showed that the participants who were in the incidental learning group outperformed the intentional learning group considering both the receptive and productive knowledge of collocations. Moreover, it was observed that the kind of improvement with receptive collocations was more significant than that with productive collocations.

Key words: *collocation, incidental learning, intentional learning, receptive knowledge, productive knowledge.*

1. Introduction

Vocabulary learning is an indispensable process for EFL learners to acquire proficiency and competence in target language. It is one of the crucial elements both of acquisition of one's native language and of learning a foreign language (Morra & Camba, 2009). It is believed that having a large and varied vocabulary is the indicator

of communicative competence and it is one of the important aspects of language learning (McCrostie, 2007). To know the meaning of a word most effectively, students need to know its associations with other words (Nattinger & DeCarrio, 1992) and making this association is one of the most problematic areas for foreign language learning (Farrokh, 2012). Collocation, as a subcategory of vocabulary, is a very important part of knowledge of second language acquisition and they are essential to non-native speakers of English in order to speak or write fluently and accurately (Jaén, 2007). It is self-evident that the teaching of collocation should be a top priority in every language course (Kuo, 2009). There are two approaches to vocabulary acquisition, intentional or direct learning and incidental or indirect learning (Yali, 2011). Incidental learning is the process of learning something without the intention of doing so; it is also learning one thing while intending to learn another (Richards & Schmidt, 2002). The words that learners encounter in incidental vocabulary learning will be retained in the long term memory and could be used more confidently in different situations (Hulstijn & Laufer, 2001). Schmitt (2008) believes that intentional vocabulary learning takes place when the specific goal is to learn vocabulary, usually with an explicit focus. Nation (2001) introduced a common aspect of word knowledge, *receptive* knowledge and *productive* knowledge. The receptive and productive dimension of lexical knowledge is a bridging dimension between lexical competence and performance (Zareva, Schwanenflugel & Nikolova, 2012). Productive knowledge is usually associated with speaking and writing while receptive knowledge is associated with listening and reading (Laufer & Goldstein, 2004).

According to Richards & Schmid (2002), learning something without paying any attentions to the process of learning is incidental learning. Learning one subject can also occur incidentally in the middle of learning another thing intentionally. Read (2000) found out that native speakers acquire 70% of their mother language incidentally when they hear new vocabularies in the speech or read them in a text. From this view point, linguists suggest that ESL/EFL learners learn new words incidentally, as well. Incidental learning occurs through different ways, such as reading extensively, watching original movies, listening to the native speakers and so forth.

Coadi (2001) believes that incidental learning strongly encourage learners to have extensive reading. So, learners guess the meaning of the new vocabularies through reading. Harmer (2003) and Nation (2001) claim that extensive reading can be very enjoyable for learners when a teacher asks students, in the proper level, to select a text and read it for themselves.

Based on comprehension hypothesis of Krashen, comprehensible input is an essential condition for language improvement and extensive reading affects on developing reading fluency and at the same time new vocabularies and grammar structures are added to the previous knowledge (Krashan, 2003).

Hunt and Beglar (1998) believe that extensive reading and listening help students learn many vocabularies incidentally; therefore, encouraging learners to have extensive reading and listening give them many chances to confront with new vocabularies. Huckin and Coady (1999) hold the same idea, too. They claim that learning new vocabularies can occur by guessing the meaning of new vocabularies in

the extensive reading. These researchers agree that incidental learning is a useful approach for all EFL/ESL learners at all levels.

In order to meet an acceptable proficiency and competency in the domain of target language, learners should highly view vocabulary learning as an inevitable process. Vocabulary knowledge brings about fluent speaking and effective writing. It confirms not only receiving but also producing knowledge. It empowers learners' language skills.

Intentional vocabulary learning is defined as "a deliberate attempt to commit factual information to memory" (Hulstijn, 2011, p.1). Hulstijn, Hollander, and Greidanus (1996) state that through merely intentional vocabulary activities, it is impossible to learn the words and via listening and reading activities words must be "picked up". Intentional vocabulary learning leads to better retention, and wide vocabulary knowledge than the incidental vocabulary learning alone.

Ahmad (2011) claims that intentional vocabulary learning is not an effective approach as it is only based on synonyms, antonyms, word substitution, multiple choice, scrambled words and crossword puzzles, without paying any attention to the context. According to his study, learners memorize the words without doing any cognitive processing. As the result, only few words can be transformed into active process. On the contrary, learning new vocabularies through text can be more effective because learners can use the ability of guessing the meaning through the context.

2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

This study will address the following research questions:

- 1- Does incidental learning as compared with intentional learning lead to a more successful development of the receptive knowledge of collocations?
- 2- Does incidental learning as compared with intentional learning lead to a more successful development of the productive knowledge of collocations?

To investigate the effects of incidental learning on the development of the receptive and productive knowledge of collocations the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₀1: Incidental learning as compared with intentional learning does not lead to a more successful development of the receptive knowledge of collocations.

H₀2: Incidental learning as compared with intentional learning does not lead to a more successful development of the productive knowledge of collocations.

3. Methodology

Design

This study utilizes a quasi-experimental research design with two groups of participants. To ensure the comparability of the participants prior to the treatment, participants were given a pretest and a posttest to measure the effect of the treatment.

Procedure

Based on the study purpose and the participants' availability, 50 Persian-speaking female students participated in this study. To see whether the participants build a homogenous group in terms of their English proficiency, the researcher administered a PET test (Preliminary English Test) with 60 students who were distributed into two classes, each one containing 30 students, and chose 25 participants from each class

whose scores ranged from 65 to 75. One class formed the incidental group to be taught incidentally and the other one formed the intentional group to be taught intentionally. The participants' ages ranged from 18 to 25. All of them were studying at high-intermediate level of adult department of Iran Language Institute, Kermanshah branch. They all had studied English for at least 2 years at ILL.

A validated teacher-made pre-test in the form of a gap -filling productive test and an appropriateness of judgment receptive test were given to each group before the instructional period. The gap- filling productive test included 30 target collocations that examined two types of collocations: 15 verb-noun collocations and 15 adjective-noun collocations. The two tests were used in structural forms that allowed only one correct answer. For each blank, the initial letter of the target collocation was provided as a clue to help the participants remember the appropriate collocation. The validated teacher-made receptive test was devised to measure the participants' receptive competence of the correct English collocations. It consisted of 30 target collocations that examined two types of collocations: 15 verb-noun collocations and 15 adjective-noun collocations. The students were asked to judge whether the underlined part of a sentence was acceptable or not by circling a number corresponding to the appropriate part of the sentence. At the end of the instructional period which involved a two-month study containing 16 sessions each lasting one and a half hour, the posttests which were same tests as the pretests were applied again to see the effectiveness of the treatment. The productive test was administered first and lasted for 20 minutes; the receptive test was administered right after the participants finished the productive test and lasted for 20 minutes. Both instruments were checked, and each participant was given a number to ensure that the same participant took each of the two tests.

Treatment procedure

The researcher taught the incidental group without specific attention to focus on collocational learning. The intentional group was taught through focusing attention directly on the information to be taught.

Scoring Procedure

The set data of the tests were scored as correct or incorrect because all of the items allowed for only one possible answer. The total score for each instrument was 30 for the productive test and 30 for the receptive test. Items unanswered were counted as incorrect. Morphological errors, such as the incorrect use of verb tenses (e.g. *Governments should takes*) and spelling errors (e.g. *cauht fire*), weren't considered. The mismatched collocations that acted as distracters in the receptive test weren't counted.

4. Data Analysis

A quantitative study was held to gather data from the participants. The scores from the pretest and the posttest were subjected to an independent samples t-test to determine whether or not there were significant differences between each group's performances. The data obtained from the mentioned tests were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 16 (SPSS, 16).

As it is shown in table 4.3, the participants' scores of the productive pretest in both incidental and intentional groups are almost similar and there is no significant difference between the participants in both groups concerning their productive

knowledge of collocations based on the observed significance (.238) which is larger than the probability level of .05.

Table 4.2
T-test for Productive Pretest

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Incidental	25	9.84	1.46	1.195	48	.238
Intentional	25	9.40	1.11			

To compare both groups' participants receptive knowledge of collocations on the pretest, another t-test was run. According to the meaningful level of significance obtained from data analysis which equals .153 and comparing that with alpha level which was set at 0.05, we can conclude that the participants' scores of the receptive pretest in both incidental and intentional groups are almost similar and there is no significant difference between the participants in both groups concerning their receptive knowledge of collocations.

Table 4.3
T-test for Receptive Pretest

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Incidental	25	9.24	1.26	-1.450	48	.153
Intentional	25	9.76	1.26			

To find the impact of the treatment, the same test as the pretest was administered as the post test. Based on the significance obtained from data analysis on the productive collocation test which equals 0.000 and comparing that with alpha level which is 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the effect of incidental and intentional learning on the development of the productive knowledge of collocations.

Table 4.4
T-test for Productive Posttest

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Incidental	25	22.36	2.36	6.35	48	.000
Intentional	25	18.38	1.67			

Based on the significance obtained from data analysis on the collocation receptive test which equals 0.000 and comparing that with alpha level which is 0.05, we can be

certain that there is a significant difference between the effect of incidental and intentional learning on the development of the receptive knowledge of collocations.

Table 4.5
T-test for Receptive Posttest

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Incidental	25	23.08	2.30	5.392	48	0.000
Intentional	25	19.36	2.56			

The result of the data analysis shows that the hypothesis which states that there is no difference between the effect of incidental and intentional learning on the development of receptive knowledge of collocations is rejected.

The result of the data analysis shows that the hypothesis which states that there is no difference between the effect of incidental and intentional learning on the development of productive knowledge of collocations is rejected.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The first question of this study is related to whether incidental learning of collocations can improve the development of the receptive knowledge of collocations. To answer this question, the preset author tested two groups of participants namely incidental and intentional groups. The results of the current study revealed that the participants in the incidental group achieved significantly higher scores on the receptive posttest than the participants in the intentional group (in the incidental group, the mean for the receptive posttest was 23.08; in the intentional group, the mean for the receptive posttest was 19.36).

The second question is related to whether incidental learning of collocations can improve the development of the productive knowledge of collocations. To answer this question, the preset author tested two groups of participants namely incidental and intentional groups. The results of the current study revealed that the participants in the incidental group achieved significantly higher scores on the productive posttest than the participants in the intentional group (in the incidental group, the mean for the productive posttest was 22.36; in the intentional group it was 18.38).

By comparing the receptive and productive tests, one can find that the participants in both groups outperformed on the receptive test as compared with the productive test. It means that, as the other skills, language learners have more problems on the production than the reception of language. The data obtained from the tests revealed a significant difference between participants' receptive and productive knowledge of collocations. The learners' receptive knowledge was broader than the learner's productive knowledge. On the posttest, the means of the receptive tests were higher than the means of the productive tests in both incidental and intentional groups. That receptive knowledge typically precedes productive mastery is not surprising. It requires a more serious care on the part of language teachers to pay the same attention on the production of collocations as they do on the reception.

6. Conclusion

Vocabulary knowledge has an important role in almost all areas of language learning. Without understanding the text's vocabulary, text comprehension is impossible either in one's native language or in a foreign language. Some researchers now claim that compared to the other components of language, vocabulary is the most essential one. No matter how skilled students are at grammar, communication will cease without the words to convey meaning. Language teaching methodologies have attached great importance to vocabulary learning, and sometimes it has been neglected. One of the principal controversial issues in vocabulary teaching and learning in the field is how to identify significant approaches and strategies to teaching and learning vocabularies. Two approaches for vocabulary learning are incidental and intentional learning and one aspect of vocabulary learning is collocational learning which can be taught incidentally or intentionally. Previous research on collocations has proved learners' inadequate proficiency of production and reception of collocations. The present study tried to investigate the development of the receptive and productive knowledge of collocations through incidental learning vs. intentional learning. The results of the data analysis rejected the hypotheses of the study. It was found that incidental learning of collocations led to a better acquisition of the receptive and productive knowledge of collocations as manifested by the taken tests from the participants. Also, the participants' receptive knowledge of collocations proved to be broader than their productive collocational knowledge.

In summary, the results revealed that collocations are a source of difficulty for English language learners. Therefore, L2 curriculum designers and teachers should pay more attention to collocations.

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